

ISic3334

Funerary inscription for Xenokritos son of Hephaistokles, of Massalia

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2013.10.04

Last Change

2018-02-23 - Jonathan Prag added bibl

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in May 1915 by Orsi in the

Coordinates

37.0750458, 15.2590759

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 36613

Physical Description

A limestone block, intact and finished on the front, left, right and rear faces.

The upper surface is uneven, although there is a clear margin at the top edge, suggesting that another stone originally stood on top of this one. The stone is broken across the bottom.

Dimensions

Height 31.2 cm

Width 36.3 cm

Depth 29 cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek text engraved across the full width of the front face. The third line is slightly smaller than the first two. There is damage to the left margin of all three lines, and across the lower edge of the third line. The face is weathered and the letters are faint, especially at the end of the second line.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Very regularly and elegantly engraved letters without serifs, wide forms, evenly

spaced. Sigma has diverging top and bottom bars; epsilon short middle bar; omicron

perfectly round, smaller than the other letters (c.21 mm) and mid-line; omega is

round, smaller than other letters, and open at the bottom; alpha has straight bar;

kappa has full-length legs; phi has a elliptical eye. The letters are very similar to those of dated Hieronian inscriptions, i.e. third century BC.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 35 mm

Line 2: 35-37 mm

Line 3: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 13-15 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 15 mm

Text

1. Ξενόκριτος Ἡφαιστοκλέ[ου] Μασσαλιώτης

Apparatus

Orsi 1915 and in the museum inventory read the final two letters of line 2, now no longer

visible on the stone.

A trace is visible on the stone of the upper right of the initial M

Translation

Xenokritos, son of Hephaistokles, the Massaliote

Commentary

The stone was lost at some point after 1929 when it was mentioned in Libertini's guide to the old museum. Manganaro was unable to find it in the early 1990s. The patronym Ἡφαιστοκλήης is rare: LGPN records two instances from Athens, one from Kolophon in Ionia, one from Istros in Scythia, and four from Lycia (Myra and Olympos) (http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=ΗΦΑΙΣΤΟΚΛΗΣ [http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=ΗΦΑΙΣΤΟΚΛΗΣ]). The name perhaps supports the observations of L. Robert regarding the presence of Ionian elements among Massaliote names, and especially the prevalence of theophoric compound names (Robert, L. 1968. *Noms de personnes et civilisation grecque, I. Noms de personnes dans Marseille grecque*. *Journal des Savants*, année 1968, 197-213 [DOI: 10.3406/jds.1968.1181 [http://www.persee.fr/doc/jds_0021-8103_1968_num_4_1_1181]] = *Opera Minora Selecta*, VII (Amsterdam

1990), 141-57 = Choix d'écrits (ed. D. Rousset, Paris 2007), 131-44; cf. Mullen, A. 2013. Southern Gaul and the Mediterranean. Multilingualism and Multiple Identities in the Iron Age and Roman Periods (Cambridge), 137-143). The name Ξενόκριτος on the other hand is very common, but principally in Delphi and Thessaly, with only a single western instance attested, from Lokroi Epizephyrioi in the archaic period.

Xenokritos is not by any means the only Massaliote known at Syracuse or in Sicily. Orsi 1915 speculates on a merchant. Manganaro 1992 links this text to wide range of other material, both coinage and epigraphic attestations of Massaliotes, with further discussion in Manganaro, G. (1994). Massalia-Sardegna-Sicilia: la rotta commerciale in epoca ellenistica. Le ravitaillement en blé de Rome et des centres urbains des débuts de la République jusqu'au Haut Empire (Actes du colloque international de Naples 1991) (Naples-Rome), 261-265.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645582

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 185 fig.5

Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani*. Roma. At 121

Manganaro, G. 1992. Massalioti per il Mediterraneo: tra Spagna, Sardegna e Sicilia. In Bonello Lai, M.(eds.), *Sardinia antiqua: Studi in onore di Piero Meloni in occasione del suo settantesimo compleanno*. Cagliari. pp. 195-206. At 199 fig.3

Dimartino, A. 2005. Siracusa: fonti epigrafiche. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G.(eds.), *Bibliografia topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle isole tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 59-128. At 85 no.13

Prag, J.R.W. 2017. Un unpublished funerary inscription with bichrome painted relief lettering from Hellenistic Syracuse (I.Sicily 3387). *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 203: 119-130.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-10): ISic3334. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022699>

Photo J. Prag